

Editorial

RAUSP Management Journal: changes and challenges for 2018

RAUSP Management Journal: mudanças e desafios para 2018

Dear RAUSP Management Journal readers,

We begin this edition wishing everyone a creative and innovative year of 2018!

Always in the sense of continuously improving RAUSP – Management journal, we have implemented many new features since the beginning of 2017. . . The first one is the new composition of our Editorial Board, which brings renowned researchers from several institutions, namely: Anabella Davila (EGADE Business School Monterrey, Monterrey, N.L., Mexico); Anna Grandori (Bocconi University, Milan, Italy); Danny Pimentel Claro (Insper, São Paulo, SP, Brazil); Hyungseok (David) Yoon (Leeds University Business School, Leeds, United Kingdom); Fredrik Tell (Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden); Heitor Almeida (University of Illinois, Illinois, USA); Joseph F. Hair, Jr. (University of South Alabama, Mobile, Alabama, USA); Juana Catalina Garcia Duque (Universidad de Los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia); Keith Jackson (University of London, London, United Kingdom); Lourdes Casanova (Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, USA); Luiz F. Mesquita (Arizona State University, Phoenix, Arizona, USA); Manuel Rocha Armada (University of Minho); Maria Alejandra Gonzalez-Perez (EAFIT Medellín University, Medellín, Antioquia, Colombia); Maria Tereza Leme Fleury (Fundação Getúlio Vargas, São Paulo, SP, Brazil); Marlei Pozzebon (HEC Montréal, Québec, Montréal, Canada); Sérgio Giovanetti Lazzarini (Insper, São Paulo, SP, Brazil); Sergio Olavarrieta (University of Chile); Won-Ho Kim (Hankuk University of Foreign Studies, Seoul, Korea). In addition to the expected role of contributing with their suggestions, the members of the Editorial Board have committed to work continuously on the dissemination of the knowledge made available through this journal, by inviting new readers, potential authors and reviewers to increase the quality and relevance of RAUSP even further.

Our second innovation was the decision to take on “RAUSP – Management Journal” as our official title under a new ISSN. This decision was based on the receptivity of our collaborators and readers with the previous choice to publish all of the

articles in English. By following recommendations from specialists in publishing (ABEC, 2017; ANPAD, 2014), we have been working hard to improve our bibliometric indexes, notably the impact factor. Our purpose is to keep enhancing the visibility of the publication, so that both Brazilian and foreign researchers will increasingly consider RAUSP – Management Journal as a priority outlet for the dissemination of the results of their cutting-edge research. The previous introduction of the *thinkbox* section had initially fulfilled the objective of expanding the reach of the publication. By publishing articles written by researchers with an international reputation, we aim to disseminate the contents of our journal beyond domestic boundaries. The decision has already created a virtuous cycle, positively affecting the level of citations received by RAUSP – Management Journal.

Furthermore, we think that RAUSP – Management Journal should also make public the contributions that are relevant to practitioners: companies’ managers, entrepreneurs, and public sector’s agents. We always invite our authors, often without much success, to provide executive summaries of the approved articles, aiming to widen the dissemination of the research outcomes on blogs and social media, as important as it is today.

Our invited *thinkbox* article addresses an issue that has become increasingly important for scholars worldwide: how to better measure the impacts of our researches. In his paper **The Measurement of Social Impact and Opportunities for Research in Business Administration**, Sergio Lazzarini discusses new and more effective forms of assessing how management researchers can also contribute to organizations to achieve their social and economic goals.

As usual in our journal, the articles of this edition present a great diversity of themes and methodological approaches.

Claude Ménard, in his theoretical paper **Research Frontiers of New Institutional Economics**, expands the discussions on the New Institutional Economics, emphasizing its new approaches and contemplating the future possibilities for the researches in this area.

Elói Junior Damke, Fernando Antonio Prado Gimenez, and Joice F. Wendling Damke, in the paper **Strategic configurations**

and performance: a study in micro and small business retailers, verify which strategy configurations – strategy development process, strategy content, entrepreneurial attitude, administrative mode and perceived environmental uncertainty – are associated with the performance of small-sized clothing retail businesses.

Marconi Freitas-da-Costa, Carlos Everaldo Costa, Claudio Felisoni de Angelo, and Walter Fernando Araújo de Moraes, in the paper **Perceived Competitive Advantage of Soccer Clubs: A study based on the resource-based view (RBV)**, analyze how professional soccer clubs perceive the competitive advantages they possess in the light of the resource-based view, given their internal resources and external aspects.

Marina Amado Bahia Gama, Rodrigo Bandeira-de-Mello, and Juliano Danilo Spuldaro, in the article **Political Strategy and the Growth of Business Groups**, investigate how companies and government interactions affect business groups' decisions on growth.

Vinicius Augusto Brunassi Silva and Richard Saito, in the paper **Corporate restructuring: empirical evidence on the approval of the reorganization plan**, contemplate how reorganization plans are considered by the main actors involved in their approval.

Fernando Filardi, Filippe Delarissa Barros, and Adalberto A. Fischmann, in the article **Business Strategies for the Bottom of the Pyramid: Multiple Case Studies of Large Companies in the Pacified Communities of Rio de Janeiro**, analyze the strategies that large companies have been using to operate in the Base of the Pyramid (BoP) markets.

Francisco José da Costa, Marcelo de Souza Bispo and Rita de Cássia de Faria Pereira, in the paper **Dropout and retention of undergraduate students in management: a study at a Brazilian federal university**, perform a study in a Brazilian Federal

University to analyze why undergraduate management students remain in their courses or decide to quit them. Manuella Maia Ribeiro, Eduardo H. Diniz, Lya Cynthia Porto de Oliveira, and Sarah Martins Faleiros, in their article **Information systems and intergovernmental relations in Brazilian social policies: a study on users' adaptations to the local context**, seek to identify barriers to the adoption of information

systems in Brazilian federal government social policies at the local level.

Rubens Nunes, in his paper **An attempt to classify plural forms of governance**, presents a classification of cases of plural governance structures, based on the rationale behind the choice of a combination of simple governance structures.

André Limp, Sergio Fernando Loureiro Rezende, and Angela França Versiani, in the paper **Customer Relationships and Interdependences in the Internationalization Process of the Firm** use a case study of a born-global firm from an emerging country to analyze the influence of customer relationships in driving interdependences between the firm's international trajectories.

Finally, Maria Renata Martinez Barral, Felipe Garcia Ribeiro, Mario Duarte Canever, in the article **Influence of the university environment in the entrepreneurial intention in public and private universities**, analyze the entrepreneurial intention (EI) in different higher education institutional environments, for both public and private universities.

We wish everyone a very good year of 2018 with excellent readings.

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Editor-in-Chief

Maria Sylvia Macchione Saes*
*Universidade de São Paulo, Faculdade de Economia,
Administração e Contabilidade, São Paulo, SP, Brazil*

Co-editor

Flavio Hourneaux Junior
*Universidade de São Paulo, Faculdade de Economia,
Administração e Contabilidade, São Paulo, SP, Brazil*

E-mail: editor.rausp@usp.br (M.S. Saes).

Available online 16 January 2018